

Organisation	VID Specialized University
Responsible person	Vice-Rector for Research
Contact Person	Trine Powell, Research Administration
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Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

VID signed the Agreement of Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) autumn 2023. The purpose of the action plan is to identify how VID aims to meet the obligations in ARRA and implement the changes in response to the commitments therein, within the 5-year period.

Obligations

- Allocate resources to improve assessments of research and researchers
- Assess and develop criteria, tools and processes with a focus on flexibility and different institutional needs
- Engage in knowledge transfer
- Training and staff development

Guiding principles for the assessment and evaluation of research and researchers (NOR-CAM)

ARRA provides a common direction for reforming research assessment practices. Whilst the tradition in Norway is to rely less on quantitative indicators in research assessment, there is still scope for improving research assessment and associated processes and procedures. The Norwegian Association for Higher Education Institutions (UHR) has developed its own toolbox for research career assessment in the form of matrix (NOR-CAM) and initiated a national network for sharing best practise. VID has engaged in the national network, embraced NOR-CAM and developed its own institutional matrix (VID-CAM) in line with the principles of NOR-CAM.

The matrix is divided into five competence areas, with research competence being the prominent. This competency area is subdivided into research results, research process and research leadership with a non-exhaustive list of examples. One of the intentions of the matrix is to demonstrate a broader range of competencies that can be considered in recruitment and promotion processes.

VID aims to meet the COARA commitments principally through implementation of recommendations of VID-CAM.

About the institution

VID is a specialized university with high academic teaching and research ambitions. VID educates leaders and professionals for service in the health, social and educational sectors and the church. VID conducts research, development and innovation on a high international level within the academic areas of health and social sciences, pedagogy, culture and social studies, management, diaconia and theology.

VID has approx. 6000 students, 100 PhD students and 600 staff distributed across three campuses in Oslo, Bergen, Stavanger.

Research is principal to VIDs strategy and growth. “Promote Research” is one of the five pillars in the current strategic plan and will remain at the forefront in the next strategy period. VIDs Vice-Rector for Research is responsible for the project deliverables.

VID offers three PhD programmes: Diaconia, Values and Professional Practice, Theology and Religion and Health Science.

VID’s internal guidelines support the national goals and guidelines for open access to scientific articles from the Ministry of Education and Research and the Research Council of Norway.

Action	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
Submit COARA Action Plan					
Participate in and share best practice with NOR-CAM network (national chapter)					
Sign DORA					
Submit the HRS4R application based on the Research Charter					
Develop and deliver dissemination plan for sharing reform practise internally across the institution					
Monitor and evaluate the implementation phase of the COARA action plan and review and revise accordingly					
Report annually on progress to the Research Committee (FU)					
Promote diversity of careers prospects with careers information and advice and mentoring schemes					
Incorporate VID-CAM in careers guidance for PhD and Early Career Researchers					
Actively engage in EURAXESS and ERA Talent Careers in Academia Hub networks to share experiences					
Commit resources to the implementation of the action plan (research administration, central administration and academic staff)					
Develop training for HR to support leaders recruiting academic staff to recognise diversity of research competences					
Meet the actions of the HRS4R action plan in relation to the Research Charter					

Internal revision of guidelines for a broader competency assessment in relation to recruitment and promotion to academic position (VID-CAM)					
Establish internal guidelines for competency requirements for different academic positions					
Revise guidelines for appraisals to feature VID-CAM (medarbejdersamtaler) for academic staff					
Deliver training material on development of research assessment internally					
Develop guidelines on research assessment (for committees /panels)					